

Network Analysis of Multi-omics Data Identifies Shared Genes and Pathways Underlying the Risk of Allergic Diseases and IgE Production

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Both genetic and epigenetic mechanisms influence risk of allergic diseases (AD) and Immunoglobulin E (IgE) levels, a key intermediate phenotype in allergy. Integration of omics data related to AD and IgE can provide more insight into allergy-related mechanisms.

We applied network analysis to summary-level data from a publicly available genome-wide association study (GWAS) of AD (242,569 subjects, GWAS catalog: GCST005038), and from epigenome-wide association studies (EWAS) of IgE levels based on targeted bisulfite sequencing and conducted separately in 343 asthmatics and 370 non-asthmatics from the EGEA study. We used the STRING protein-protein interaction network as background and the SigMod method to identify modules (sub-networks) enriched in trait-associated genes. We then investigated the relationships between the AD-GWAS gene module and each IgE-EWAS gene module.

We identified three modules of (i) 292 genes and 1,233 interactions derived from AD-GWAS; (ii) 251 genes and 720 interactions derived from IgE-EWAS in asthmatics; (iii) 205 genes and 534 interactions derived from IgE-EWAS in non-asthmatics. More than 99% of the genes from each module were nominally associated ($P \leq 0.05$) with their respective trait. The AD-GWAS module shared eight and seven genes, respectively, with IgE-EWAS modules (asthmatics and non-asthmatics). A significant proportion of AD-GWAS module genes directly interacts with genes from each IgE-EWAS module (more than 70%, $P < 10^{-5}$). All three modules were enriched for pathways related to antigen presentation in the context of HLA complex. This study shows shared biological mechanisms underlying AD-GWAS and IgE-EWAS gene modules. Further functional characterization of these modules is underway.

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